

ARTICLE

OVERCOMING THE GAP BETWEEN KNOWING AND DOING: THE IMPLEMENTATION OF METACOGNITIVE-BASED LEARNING IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING IN INDONESIA

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ABSTRAK

English language learning in Indonesia continues to face challenges, particularly the gap between students' knowledge of effective learning strategies and the actual application of those strategies in practice. Many students still assess learning success based on exam scores or memorization skills rather than on their awareness of managing their own learning processes. This condition contributes to low higher-order thinking skills and stagnant English development despite years of study. Numerous studies show that metacognitive strategies can help students plan, monitor, and evaluate their learning independently. Some research highlights metacognition as the ability to "think about one's thinking," while other studies emphasize that metacognitive strategies significantly improve reading comprehension and self-regulated learning skills. Local findings also support the effectiveness of these strategies across various educational levels, from elementary schools to universities (Kung & Aziz, 2020). The research method used in this article is a literature review by examining various international and local studies related to the implementation of metacognitive-based learning in English language instruction. The findings indicate that the application of metacognitive strategies can enhance deep text processing, listening skills, and students' learning regulation abilities.

Keywords: *evaluation, knowing–doing gap, reading, MBL, metacognition, monitoring, planning.*

INTRODUCTION

In Indonesia, many students still assess learning success based on exam scores, class rankings, and the ability to memorize material or formulas, rather than on a deep understanding of how to manage their own learning processes. This situation affects their higher-order learning abilities and leads to stagnant English proficiency even though the language has been taught for many years. A metacognitive-strategy-based approach has been proven to improve students' ability to plan, monitor, and evaluate their learning independently. In the context of English reading comprehension, the application of metacognitive strategies has also been

shown to enhance deeper text understanding rather than relying solely on memorization. Because of this, integrating metacognitive-based learning into English language instruction can be a solution to the gap between “knowing” effective learning strategies and “doing” them in actual practice (Sari, 2021).

Several studies show that the application of metacognitive strategies in reading instruction can help students from elementary to high school better understand texts in depth, rather than simply reading through memorization. For example, research on elementary school students reveals that metacognitive strategies such as reading strategies, predicting content, and creating effective summaries improve students’ reading comprehension. At the secondary school level, interventions using metacognitive strategies have been proven to enhance students’ reading skills and learning regulation. Other research indicates that students who use metacognitive strategies, such as evaluating and reevaluating their reading outcomes are better able to comprehend complex texts and retain information (Kung & Aziz, 2020). Therefore, it is essential for English instruction from elementary to high school to integrate metacognitive-based learning so that students not only “know” effective learning strategies but also genuinely and consistently put them into practice.

To address this issue, an approach is needed that can help students understand their own thinking processes. This approach is known as **metacognition**. Metacognition is defined as an individual’s ability to “think about one’s thinking,” which refers to the ability to be aware of, understand, and control the thinking strategies used during learning. In general, metacognition consists of two main components: **metacognitive knowledge** (knowledge about learning strategies, learning conditions, and one’s own abilities) and **metacognitive regulation** (the ability to manage the learning process through planning, monitoring, and evaluation). With these two components, students not only know what they need to learn but also understand how they learn, why certain strategies are more effective, and how to improve their strategies when facing difficulties (Kusuma & Nisa, 2019).

In the context of English language learning, metacognition plays an important role because it helps students become more independent learners. Through a metacognitive-based learning approach, students are trained to create learning plans, monitor their understanding during the learning process, and evaluate their learning outcomes reflectively. These components planning, monitoring, and evaluating, are part of cognitive regulation that has been identified in classical models of metacognition. In the context of second or foreign language learning, researchers have shown that by developing cognitive awareness and control, students can manage their learning processes more effectively than by relying solely on memorization (Cemini & Gempes, 2025).

As an illustration of implementation, metacognition can be applied across various educational levels. At the elementary school level, teachers can help students develop the habit of setting simple learning goals, such as writing down the targets they want to achieve before starting a lesson. After the activity, students are also guided to create learning notes or reflection journals. This practice aligns with the findings of *Metacognitive Strategies in Teaching Reading to Primary Students*, which emphasizes that applying metacognitive strategies in

reading particularly through planning and reflection stages has proven effective in improving reading comprehension among elementary students (Tandean, 2020). At the junior high school level, teachers can encourage students to check their own understanding of texts or lessons through self-questioning techniques. In addition, teachers may ask students to perform think-aloud activities, in which they verbalize their thought processes while completing tasks, as a way to monitor metacognition. This approach is supported by findings from *The Metacognitive Self-Regulation of Students Toward English Learning Achievement at XI SMPN 2 Duampanua Pinrang*, which shows that students' self-regulation and metacognitive abilities have a positive and significant relationship with their English learning achievement (Purnama et al., 2025). At the senior high school level, the application of metacognitive strategies in English learning, especially when reading multimodal texts can help students become more aware and reflective of their learning processes. For example, before reading, students can plan their reading goals. During reading, they can monitor their understanding and take notes. After reading, they can reflect to evaluate how well they comprehended the text. Research conducted in rural areas (regions far from major cities) suggests that students who apply these strategies are able to improve their English reading skills because metacognitive strategies encourage them to be more active in organizing and assessing their own learning processes. Thus, integrating metacognitive strategies in senior high school English classes helps students become more independent and effective learners (Manalu, 2024).

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Gap between Knowing and Doing in English Learning

In practice, this phenomenon shows a gap between knowing and applying reading strategies. Many EFL students actually know techniques such as making predictions, monitoring comprehension, or summarizing a text, but not all of them feel the need or have the habit to use these strategies consistently. As a result, metacognitive strategies that should help them understand texts more deeply are often only used by students with intermediate abilities, while lower-level students frequently revert to simpler methods such as memorizing vocabulary or guessing sentence meanings, which are less effective in the long term. These findings emphasize that successful reading is not only about knowing the strategies but also about being aware of and consistently applying them (Sulistiyowati et al., 2022). Research in Indonesia also finds that when students encounter more complex or multimodal texts, they tend to rely only on spontaneous problem-solving strategies, without adequate planning to support their comprehension. This condition highlights that a gap still exists between “knowing learning strategies” and “actually applying them correctly in practice.” In other words, successful learning is not just about understanding learning theories but about how students consciously regulate their own learning processes.

Students become more aware of how they learn and think through a metacognitive-based learning approach. They do not simply learn automatically or follow the flow of

instruction; instead, they actively reflect on their own learning processes through metacognitive practices. This approach encourages students to become more aware of their thinking and learning through three main stages: planning, monitoring, and evaluating. These strategies make the learning process more structured and less automatic. In learning English, especially when students read expository texts, the application of metacognitive strategies is crucial because it enables them to recognize how they understand the text, deal with difficulties, and assess whether the strategies they use are effective. Research shows that the use of metacognitive strategies significantly improves students' comprehension of expository texts. In this way, students do not merely focus on achieving exam scores but also develop metacognitive awareness of their learning processes (Suharni et al., 2024).

Application of Metacognitive-Based Learning in English Language Learning

In English language learning, awareness and the use of metacognitive strategies have been proven to significantly influence students' achievement. This shows that EFL (English as a Foreign Language) students who actively use metacognitive strategies, such as planning how to read, monitoring their comprehension, and evaluating their reading outcomes (Zhang & Seepho, 2013) tend to achieve higher reading scores compared to those who rarely use such strategies. Thus, a metacognitive-based learning approach can help students become independent learners who do not merely memorize but truly understand, control, and improve their learning processes according to their needs.

Local research also supports these findings. A study on Indonesian university students found that problem-solving strategies were the most frequently used, followed by global reading strategies and supporting strategies as complements for understanding texts. Beyond reading skills, the application of metacognitive strategies in listening classes has also been proven to improve students' listening performance (Sulistiyowati et al., 2022).

These strategies show that metacognition and self-regulated learning positively improve students' self-regulation abilities from elementary to senior high school. Students who are able to plan, monitor, and evaluate their learning, as well as regulate themselves independently, tend to be more confident and effective in solving problems (Arianto & Hanif, 2024). Below is an example of a table of student activities in Metacognitive-Based Learning.

No.	MBL	Goal	Elementary School (Grades 1-6)	Junior High School (Grades 7-9)	Senior High School (10-12)
1.	Planning	Helping students prepare learning goals and strategies	With the teacher's assistance, students determine their	Students write their goals in a notebook, choose learning	Students set both short-term and long-term academic

			learning goals, list the materials and tools needed, and the teacher helps them create a simple schedule.	strategies (such as reading, note-taking, asking questions), and plan the time needed for each task.	goals, identify the best methods for completing specific tasks, and create an organized independent study plan.
2.	Monitoring	Students monitor their understanding during learning	Students raise their hands when they do not understand, the teacher provides a simple comprehension checklist, and they work in small groups to help one another.	Students use self-questioning (“Do I understand this yet?”), fill in graphic organizers to record key ideas, and talk with peers to confirm their understanding.	Students use learning journals to track progress, apply structured note-taking techniques (such as Cornell notes, mind-maps, etc.), and reflect while completing assignments or projects.
3.	Evaluating	Assessing understanding and the strategies used	Students explain what they have learned; the teacher provides a simple rubric to evaluate tasks; students identify one thing they have understood and one thing they have not yet understood.	Students assess their own and their group’s learning outcomes, write down difficult aspects and explain why they were difficult, and the teacher gives students the opportunity to provide comments.	Students conduct rubric-based self-evaluations; choose ways to improve future assignments; present their learning outcomes; and receive feedback.
4.	Reflection	Recognizing strengths and areas for improvement	Students answer short reflection	After the lesson, students write	Students produce reports

			questions from the teacher.	regular reflections.	containing in-depth reflections (portfolios).
5.	Regulation	Adjusting strategies based on evaluation	When difficulties arise, the teacher helps modify the learning approach.	Students adjust their independent learning methods.	Students adapt their learning methods according to reflection results and goals.

The Relationship between Metacognitive-Based Learning and Critical Thinking

Due to cultural influences that emphasize obedience to teachers and a lack of habit in expressing personal opinions, students in Indonesia often become passive learners. As a result, critical thinking skills are not fully developed. The 2013 Curriculum actually attempts to address this issue by implementing various methods such as the scientific approach, discovery learning, problem-based learning, and project-based learning. These methods provide students with opportunities to actively analyze, evaluate, and construct their own understanding. As stated in various approaches, active engagement in the thinking process is essential to prepare students for future real-world challenges. Metacognitive-based learning encourages students to plan, monitor, and evaluate their own thinking processes, allowing them not only to acquire knowledge but also to develop the ability to process it independently and think critically (Maro, 2016).

CONCLUSION

English language learning in Indonesia still faces many challenges, particularly the gap between *knowing* effective learning approaches and *consistently applying* them in practice. Many students possess knowledge of various strategies for reading and learning, yet they are not accustomed to using them consciously. As a result, learning processes often rely on outdated methods such as memorization or guessing text content, which do not support deep comprehension. Metacognitive-based learning offers a practical solution to these issues. By teaching students to plan, monitor, and evaluate their learning processes, this approach focuses on increasing self-awareness and the ability to regulate their own learning strategies. A range of local and international studies shows that metacognitive strategies can enhance students' ability to regulate their learning, read effectively, and improve listening skills across different educational levels. Integrating metacognitive-based learning from elementary to senior high

school will help students build more reflective and independent learning habits. In this way, they not only understand English material but also develop higher-order thinking skills and long-term learning abilities. Ultimately, the success of English language learning is determined not only by how much students know, but by how consistently they can manage and apply effective learning strategies in their daily lives.

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